

References

1. K. N. RAO and THAMMANNA, "Plant Wealth of Tirumala", TTD Publication, Tirupati, 1980, p. 72.
2. H. WAGNER, H. DANNINGER, M. A. IYENGAR, O. SELIGMANN, L. FARKAS, S. S. SUBRAMANIAN and A. G. R. NAIR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1971, 104, 2681.
3. J. B. HARBORNE, *Phytochemistry*, 1963, 2, 327.

Flavonoid Glucuronides from the Leaves of *Clerodendron linearis*

MOKHTAR ALI NIA and D. GUNASEKAR*

Department of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara University,
Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 25 March 1991, accepted 23 April 1991

*CLERODENDRON linearis*¹ Linn. (Verbenaceae) is a tall shrub grown in gardens as winter ornamental. In the absence of any record of work on this plant, the leaves of this species have been examined. In the present study we report the isolation and characterisation of three flavone-*O*-glucuronides, viz. luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide, chrysoeriol-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide and apigenin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide.

The dried defatted leaves (2 kg) of *C. linearis* (procured from the university campus) were exhaustively extracted with methanol. The methanol concentrate was solvent-fractionated successively with hexane, ether and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate-soluble fraction on pc examination (n-BuOH-HOAc-H₂O, 6 : 1 : 2) revealed the presence of three bands labelled as CL-1, CL-2 and CL-3 in order of increasing *R_f* values. They were separated by preparative pc (BAW, 6 : 1 : 2) and eluted by methanol. All these compounds were characterised by uv, pmr, cmr, mass, acid and enzymatic hydrolysis studies, and by direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir). CL-1 furnished yellow needles (60 mg), m.p. 180–82° (MeOH), [α]_D²⁵ – 110° (pyridine), identified as luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide²; CL-2 furnished bright yellow needles (80 mg), m.p. 184–85° (MeOH), [α]_D²⁵ – 87° (pyridine), characterised as chrysoeriol-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide³; CL-3 yielded pale yellow needles (90 mg), m.p. 172–73° (MeOH), [α]_D²⁵ – 92° (water), identified as apigenin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide².

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. H. Wagner, Director, Institut für Pharmazeutische Biologie der Universität München, West Germany, for providing spectral data and authentic samples of luteolin-7-*O*-glucuronide and apigenin-7-*O*-glucuronide, and to Prof. J. B. Harborne, The University of Reading, Berkshire, U.K., for an authentic sample of chrysoeriol-7-*O*-glucuronide.